

New Methods for the Selective Glycosylation of Flavonoid Compounds

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IN the thirties of this century, Géza Zemlén, Professor of Organic Chemistry at the Technical University of Budapest, initiated an extensive research work for syntheses proving the structure of flavonoid glycosides. In continuation of this tradition, we have endeavoured to develop synthetic methods of general scope allowing the unambiguous synthesis of any representative of this group of compounds, thus affording verification of their structures. The timeliness of this work was enhanced by the fact that during the last decade the number of flavonoid glycosides isolated from different plants increased from eighty to four hundred. The structures of these compounds are extremely varied: there are many variations in both the nature of the sugar moiety and its position of attachment to the aglycone. In addition to a great number of monoglycosides, many bis-glycosides are also known.

In the course of the development of a generally applicable selective synthesis of flavonoid mono- and bis-glycosides, essentially three part-problems are to be solved:

1. Synthesis of properly protected aglycones, to which the sugar component(s) can be attached at the required position.

2. Preparation of the active sugar components (usually acetohalogeno-sugars), suitable for coupling.

3. Efficient effecting of the coupling reaction, including the isolation of the product and removal of the protective groups.

The key step of a selective synthesis is evidently the preparation of the protected aglycone mentioned above. Our methods developed for this step are illustrated here on the example of quercetin mono- and bis-glycosides. The flavonoid aglycone occurring most frequently in nature is *quercetin* (3, 3', 4', 5, 7-penta-hydroxyflavone); more than 80 glycosides of this

Quercetin

compound have been isolated so far from various plants. The possible monoglucosides and four natural bis-glycosides are listed below,

<i>Monoglucosides</i>	<i>Trivial name</i>	<i>Occurrence and first isolation</i>
Quercetin-3-glucoside	Isoquercitrin	<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i> ¹
-5-glucoside	—	<i>Lamium album</i> ²
-7-glucoside	Quercimeritrin	<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i> ¹
-3'-glucoside	—	<i>Pseudotsuga taxifolia</i> ³
-4'-glucoside	Spiraeoside	<i>Spiraea ulmaria</i> ⁴
<i>Bis-glycosides</i>		
Quercetin-4', 7-bis-glucoside	—	<i>Allium cepa</i> ⁵
-3, 4'-bis-glucoside	—	<i>Allium cepa</i> ⁵
-3, 3'-bis-glucoside	—	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> ^{6,7}
-3, 7-bis-glucoside	—	<i>Ulex europaeus</i> ⁸

Quercetin contains five phenolic hydroxyl groups which possess different acidic character owing to conjugation effects with the carbonyl group. Their different reactivity thus permits the selective attachment or removal of protective groups. It has been shown by means of ultraviolet spectroscopy that the order of decreasing acidity is, in agreement with the preparative experience, the following :

The C-3' hydroxyl group is not subject to conjugation effect from the carbonyl group, therefore it has hardly

any acidity, whereas the C-5 hydroxyl is rendered non-reactive by chelation. As a matter of fact, it was this difference in the acid character of the hydroxyl groups which has been utilized in various ways for the selective syntheses of the glucosides.

The preparation of the aglycones to be used in the synthesis of quercetin-7-glucoside and -4',7-bis-glucoside was made possible by the transacylation procedure developed by our group⁹. The method is essentially a basecatalyzed intermolecular transesterification reaction, in the course of which benzoyl groups readily migrate from the hydroxyls of higher acidity to less acidic phenolic hydroxyl groups. When pentabenzoylquercetin¹⁰ is allowed to react with 2 moles of phenol in pyridine in the presence of silver carbonate, debenzoylation occurs at the C-4' and C-7 positions. If the resulting dihydroxyquercetin is now used as the benzoyl-acceptor instead of phenol, its reaction with pentabenzoylquercetin in pyridine, in the presence of silver carbonate, gives 7-hydroxyquercetin tetrabenzoate. This compound can then be glycosylated by treatment with α -aceto-bromoglucose¹¹ in the system silver oxide-quinoline; removal of the protective groups with sodium methoxide solution yields the required *quercetin-7-glucoside*¹². There is no difficulty in the analogous preparation of

the 4', 7-bis-glucoside : 3, 3', 5-tribenzoylquercetin, mentioned above, is treated with a large excess of aceto-bromoglucose and the protective groups are subsequently removed by saponification.

7-Hydroxyquercetin tetrabenzoate is the starting material also in the synthesis of *quercetin-4'-glucoside*¹³. The compound is first benzylated in the 7-position, and the protecting benzoyl group removed from the C-4' hydroxyl, which is next on the acidity scale; the product is then glycosylated. The corresponding 4'-methyl ether can, of course, be prepared with diazomethane in an analogous manner.

The first synthesis of *quercetin-3-glucoside* was achieved by us earlier¹⁴ by means of coupling quercetin 4', 7-dibenzoate¹⁵ with an equivalent amount of aceto-bromoglucose and subsequent removal of the protective groups. Our synthesis starting from rutin represents an even simpler route: complete benzylation is effected by Jurd's method¹⁶ and the sugar moiety split off in boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid. The resulting quercetin tetrabenzoate contains a free hydroxyl group only at the 3-position. Coupling is effected in quinoline in the presence of silver oxide to obtain, on saponification, the 3-glucoside of quercetin¹⁷.

Considering that the system silver oxide-quinoline is greatly similar to silver carbonate-pyridine effecting acylmigration, a conversion of the aglycone to some extent was expected; the outcome of the reaction was, however, surprisingly favourable. In addition to quercetin-3-glucoside, the 3,7-bisglucoside¹⁷ was also obtained. The same compound can be prepared by further glycosylation, under mild conditions, of quercetin-3-glucoside. The structures of both glucosides have been substantiated by their identity with the corresponding natural products, and by the preparation of their methyl ethers. Methylation of the 3-glucoside with diazomethane followed by acid hydrolysis gives

3-hydroxy-3', 4', 5, 7-tetramethoxyflavone, a known compound¹⁸; the product of similar treatment of the bis-glucoside is 3, 7-dihydroxy-3',4',5-trimethoxyflavone.

Quercetin-3, 7-bis-glucoside was isolated by Olechnowich-Stepien²⁰ from *Euonymus maackii*; on the basis of enzymatic studies he supposed that the glucose at position 3 was attached to the aglycone by an α -glycosidic linkage. However, the bis-glucoside synthesized in our work and containing β -glycosidic linkages was completely identical with the compound described by the Polish researcher. Melting point and mixed melting point determination, R_f values in chromatography, the ultraviolet and infrared spectra, as well as circular dichroism measurements gave evidence for the identity of the products and for the presence of two β -glycosidic linkages; therefore, correction of the structure derived from the enzymic degradation studies was suggested.

The preparation of *quercetin-3'-glucoside* was an entirely novel task, since no synthesis of flavon-3'-glucosides had been reported in the literature.

The aglycone required for the synthesis was 3, 4', 7-tribenzylquercetin. This compound has been made as follows: benzylation of 3, 3', 5-tribenzoylquercetin, obtained by the acyl migration reaction as described above, and subsequent debenzoylation gives 4', 7-dibenzylquercetin. This compound is identical with the substance obtainable by the partial benzylation and subsequent deacetylation of quercetin pentaacetate¹⁵. As the hydroxyl at C-3 has the highest reactivity of the three free hydroxyl groups available, treatment with one mole of benzyl chloride preponderantly gives the required 3, 4', 7-tribenzyl ether.

oxide-quinoline, with continuous addition of acetobromoglucose. Removal of the protecting groups affords the synthetic 3'-glucoside, which is in every respect identical with the natural product.

After having accomplished this synthesis, the only remaining monoglucoside of the series to be prepared was *quercetin-5-glucoside*. Success in synthesizing this compound depended on the questionable possibility of glycosylating the C-5 hydroxyl group rendered highly inactive by chelation. The required 3, 3', 4', 7-tetra-benzylquercetin aglycone was prepared by the vigorous benzylation of quercetin in dimethylformamide. The structure of the product was confirmed by its elemental analysis, positive ferric chloride reaction, ultraviolet and proton magnetic resonance spectra. Glycosylation of the only remaining free hydroxyl group could be accomplished in about 10% yield, by the gradual addition of α -acetobromoglucose during 18 hours. Chromatographic separation from the unchanged starting material followed by deacetylation and debenylation afforded quercetin-5-glucoside, identical with the natural product.

Of the bis-glucosides, the syntheses of the 4', 7- and 3', 7-derivatives have been described above along with the monoglucosides.

The synthesis of *quercetin-3-4'-bis-glucoside* was achieved starting with 7-benzylquercetin¹⁵, making use of the relatively greater reactivity just of the two hydroxyls (C-3 and C-4') to be substituted out of the four free OH groups present in the compound. Glycosylation results in two monoglucosides and one bis-glucoside; they are the 3- and 4'-monoglucoside of 7-benzylquercetin and the desired bis-glucoside. This mixture can be separated by column chromatography

Owing to the relatively poor reactivity of the C-3' hydroxyl group, attachment of the glucose moiety requires more vigorous conditions than usual: the reaction is conducted for six hours in the system silver

to a mono- and a bis-glucoside fraction; repeated glycosylation of the mixture of monoglucosides gives a further amount of the 3, 4'-bis-glucoside derivative. The free glucoside is obtained on debenylation¹⁷.

For synthesizing *quercetin-3,3'-bis-glucoside*, the required compound is *4',7-dibenzylquercetin-3-glucoside*¹⁴, the intermediate also used in the first synthesis of *quercetin-3-glucoside*. Glycosylation under vigorous conditions and removal of the protective groups in the usual way gives synthetic *quercetin-3,3'-bis-glucoside*¹⁷.

No attempt was made at synthesizing non-natural bis-glucosides.

A number of different sugar derivatives of the various methyl ethers of quercetin (rhamnetin, isorhamnetin, tamarixetin) also occur in the vegetable kingdom. By the extended application of the methods developed in our laboratory, we achieved the synthesis of a 3-and a 7-glycoside of the aglycone tamarixetin (quercetin-4'-methyl ether).

Tamarixin, i.e. tamarixetin-3-glucoside, was first isolated by Seshadri and Gupta²¹ from *Tamarix troupii*, then in 1970, by American authors²², from *Astrogalus miser*. The melting points of the two compounds widely differed, making their identity doubtful.

Tamarixetin-7-rutinoside has not been isolated from a natural source; it was prepared by Rösler *et al.*²³ by the dehydrogenation of natural hesperidin.

Our synthesis of tamarixin started from 7-benzyl-4'-hydroxy-3,3',5-tribenzoyloxyflavone, the intermediate also used in the preparation of quercetin-4'-glucoside; this compound was methylated with diazomethane

and debenzoylated to obtain 7-benzyl-4'-methoxyquercetin. Since it is the hydroxyl at C-3 which has the highest reactivity from among the three free hydroxyl groups, direct glycosylation with α -acetobromoglucose is possible. Deacetylation and debenzoylation affords synthetic tamarixin²⁴.

The melting point of the anhydrous product was in good agreement with that published by the American authors; the compound containing 2 moles of water of crystallization has a melting point different from that reported by Gupta and Seshadri²¹ or Norris and Stermitz²².

For the synthesis of tamarixetin-7-rutinoside, 7-benzyl-4'-methoxyquercetin was acetylated and then debenzoylated; coupling with α -acetobromoglucose and removal of the protective groups gave the desired compound, identical with that described by Rösler *et al.*²³.

7-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyquercetin triacetate used in the synthesis is completely converted on heating into 5-hydroxy-4'-methoxyquercetin triacetate. Such an acyl migration on the effect of thermal treatment has been observed by us earlier in the case of apigenin benzoates²⁶, and the reaction is also known in connection with partially acylated sugars²⁷.

Some of our methods developed for the selective glycosylation of quercetin have been extended to achieve the synthesis of glycosides of other flavones. This work had double purpose: study of the differences in the transacylation and selective benzyla-

tion reactions, and demonstration of the general scope of the methods. As examples, some natural glycosides of luteolin (3',4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone) and kaempferol (3,4',5,7-tetrahydroxyflavone) have been synthesized.

Luteolin

Kaempferol

Luteolin tetrabenzoate²⁸ gives, by acyl migration, the corresponding 7-hydroxy derivative, which is glycosylated and rid from the protective groups to obtain synthetic luteolin-7-rutinoside (scolymoside)²⁹, identical in all respects with the natural product³⁰.

Several monoglycosides of kaempferol, such as the 3-rutinoside, 3- and 7-rhamnosides, and the 3-robinobioside, have also been synthesized. The common starting material for preparing the 3-glycosides is 4,7-dibenzylkaempferol which in contrast with the case of quercetin cannot be made by the benzylation of either kaempferol or its tetraacetate. Therefore, 4'-benzylkaempferol was synthesized by the Kuhn-Low modification of the Allan-Robinson condensation; this compound was acylated and benzylated according to Jurd's method¹⁵ to obtain the required dibenzyl ether. Glycosylation with α -benzoylbromorhamnose³¹ readily gave kaempferol-3-rhamnoside, identical with the natural product afzelin³⁴.

Kaempferol-3-rutinoside (nicotiflorin)³² was synthesized in an analogous way, using acetobromorutinoside for the glycosylation.

Robinin, a triglycoside of kaempferol, was first isolated as early as 1852 by Zwenger and Dropke³⁶ from the leaves of *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. Its structure was established by Zemplén and Bográd³⁷ in 1941 showing the presence of a robinobiose (L-rhamnosido-D-galactose) and a rhamnose unit attached to the oxygen atoms at C-3 and C-7, respectively, of kaempferol.

Robinin

(Kaempferol-7-rhamnosido-3-galactorhamnoside)

In 1967 Maksyutina and Litvinenko³⁸ cast doubt on this structure; in fact, they stated that robinin was a mixture of four isomers. The structure suggested by Zemplén and Bográd was definitely confirmed by our total synthesis and detailed investigation of the composition. In this synthesis 4'-benzylkaempferol is glycosylated by means of acetobromorhamnose in the presence of silver oxide and quinoline; deacetylation of the product gives 4'-benzylkaempferol-7-rhamnoside. This compound is coupled with α -

benzoylbromorobinobiose³⁹, and the protecting groups are removed in the usual way. The crystalline final product of the synthesis⁴⁰ is in all respects identical with natural robinin.

We suggest that our methods developed for the selective glycosylation of flavones are suitable also for the preparation of other flavonoid glycosides.

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